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MAKTABGACHA
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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Oilaning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar estetik tarbiyasidagi o'rni	24
Abdullayeva Ma'sudaxon Abdubannayevna	
Bo'lajak informatika o'qituvchilarini pedagogik faoliyatga metodik tayyorlash texnologiyalari	27
Abdubannoyeva Muxlisaxon Iqboljon qizi, Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida bulutli xizmatlardan foydalanish zaruriyati	30
Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich, Turdaliyeva Muslimaxon Jahongir qizi	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida fortepiano chalishni o'rgatish metodikasi	34
Abduvaxobova Nilufar Abdumannon qizi	
Maktabda fizika fanini o'qitishda innovatsion yondashuv	38
Alinazarova Mahfuza	
Tasavvufdagi "komil inson" konsepsiyasining hozirgi ta'lim tizimida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv sifatida talqini	43
Aqilxonov Saidolimxon Abdurashid o'g'li	
Tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlikni shakllantirish omillari va pedagogik shart-sharoitlar	48
Choriyeva Gulbaxor Shotemirovna	
Robototexnika fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanib mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish	53
Elmonov Sirojiddin Mamadiyarovich	
Xalqaro baholash dasturlarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini baholash bo'yicha jahon tajribasi	58
Ergasheva S. T.	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda tabiiy fanlar orqali o'quvchilarning kognitiv salohiyatini rivojlantirish	61
Eshmamatova Dilnoza Jovli qizi	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning aqliy salohiyatini oshirishda tarbiyachi mahorati	64
Karimova Gulzodaxon Marufjon qizi	
Bo'lajak texnologik ta'lim o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishni takomillashtirish	68
Hojikarimova Gulasal Tadjaliyevna	
Xorijiy talabalarga o'zbek tilini o'rgatishda elektron platformalar yaratish	71
Jo'rayeva Matluba	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun raqamli ta'lim muhitini modellashtirish va uning samaradorlik omillari	74
Komilova Z. X.	
O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida muloqot madaniyati	80
M. Yu. Mahkamova	
Psixologiya fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va talabalarda tahliliy fikrlashni shakllantirish masalalari	86
Madazizova Dilfuza Raxmatullayevna	
Integrating Listening and Speaking Skills in ESP (English for Specific Purposes) Classes	90
Madina Tilavova	
Bolalarni maktabga tayyorlash jarayonida neyropedagogik yondashuvlar	94
N. O. Saidova	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalarida radiologiya fanini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarning metodologik roli	99
Nazarova Gulchexra Shuxratdjonovna	
Ijodkorlik tushunchasining mohiyati va uning ta'limdagi roli	103
Ochilova Dilbar Isroilovna	
Alaliyani boshqa nutqiy nuqsonlar bilan farqli xarakteristikasi	108
Oripova Zilola	
Ingliz tilini o'qitishda suggestopediya metodini joriy etishning samaradorligi	113
Pulatova Sitora Abdurazzoq qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalari menejerlarining kasbiy-boshqaruv kompetentligi tushunchasi va uning tarkibiy qismlari	118
Qarshiboyev Sharof Egamnazarovich	
Koordinatsion qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishning yosh badmintonchilar texnik-taktik tayyorgarligiga ta'siri	122
Qurbanova Ilmira Alisher qizi	

Blended Learning	125
Quvandikova Xadicha	
Fizika darslarida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	129
Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li	
“Qurilish jarayonlari texnologiyasi” fanida loyihalash kompetentligining tarkibiy tuzilmasi va uni raqamli ta'limga moslashtirish	135
Raxmonova Nazokat Umaraliyevna	
Vitagen texnologiyalar asosida talabalar mediamentalitetini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellekt (AI) dasturlaridan foydalanishning tahliliy modeli	140
Rustamova Nodira Rustamovna	
Talabalarda kooperativ ta'lim asosida motivatsiyani rivojlantirish usullari	145
Sitora Toshmatova	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishning zaruriyati	149
Tashibekova Munajat Xoshimovna	
Musiqqa ta'limining pedagogik asoslari va metodik tizimi	153
Toshpulatova Saida Kuzibaevna	
Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda eng samarali metodlardan foydalanish	158
Turdiyeva Shahzoda Eshdavlrat qizi	
Enhancing University Students' Self-Directed Learning Through Edtech Tools	161
Ulasheva Lobar	
Fanlararo loyiha ishlarini tashkil etish orqali o'quvchilarning dizayn fikrlash salohiyatini oshirish	164
Valiyeva Nargiza Athamboyevna	
Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojiga ega o'quvchilarning kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari.....	169
Xakimova Sarvinov Sharifjon qizi	
Sun'iy intellekt asosida yaratilgan ta'lim platformalari: samaradorlik tahlili va pedagogik yondashuvlar	173
Xanbabayev Hakimjon Ikramovich, Erkinov Jasurbek Hasanjon o'g'li	
Tasavvufdagi “muhosaba” va “tafakkur” amallarining o'z-o'zini refleksiya metodlari sifatida qo'llanilishi	176
Xoshimov Nuriddin Mamadaliyevich	
Milliy sport va ommaviy o'yinlarning badiiy-estetik ahamiyati.....	182
Yaxyayeva Sojida Abdurahimovna	
Ota-ona mehriining bola psixologiyasiga ta'siri	185
Yulchiyeva Shohsanam Dilshod qizi	
Nutq rivojlanishi orqada qolgan bolalarda qo'llaniladigan innovatsion usullari samaradorligi	189
Ahmedova Nargiza Muzaffarovna	
Факторы, сдерживающие развитие науки в контексте требований к диссертационным работам	193
Зайналов Жахонгир Расулович, Нурмухамедов Аббос Мамадалиевич, Шадманов Камолиддин Кажакджанович, Самигова Нодира Хамидуллаевна	
Структура и стратегии развития предметных компетенций	197
Наимова Мафтунабону Файзулложоновна	
Психологическая консультация: современная практика, задачи и перспективы развития	203
Раупова Шохида Ахроровна	
Подготовка будущих педагогов к инклюзивному обучению детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья: задачи и перспективы	207
Сайфутдинова Насиба Нурматовна	
Формирование иноязычной грамотности у курсантов военных вузов: социально-психологические факторы.....	211
Сулейманова Нилуфар Камилловна	
O'qituvchi shaxsiy kompetensiyasining mohiyati va pedagogik faoliyatdagi o'rni	214
Abdiraxmonova Guliston Muzaffar qizi	
Bolalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarini shakllantirish jarayonining milliy va umuminsoniy tamoyillari	218
Abdumutalipova Gulshodaxon Nurbek qizi	
Fuqarolik jamiyatida huquqiy madaniyat va uni rivojlantirish jarayonlari	221
Abdusalimova Shaxnoza Quduratullayevna	
Ta'lim menejmenti tizimida o'qituvchining nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish strategiyalari	224
Abduxalilova Iroda Nozimxonovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

O'zbekistonda yoshlarni ijtimoiy-pedagogik hamkorlikda tarbiyalashda "Uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya konsepsiyasi"ning ustuvor vazifalari	229
Abirova Umida Nazarovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida differensiyalashtirilgan dars mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishga o'rgatish (kompetentligini shakllantirish/rivojlantirish) usullari.....	232
Adhamova Diyora Sanjar qizi	
Musobaqa faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda sambochilarning energiya sarfi va tiklanish mexanizmlari tahliliy	239
Tangriyev Abdukarim Tovashevich	
Aksiologik yondashuv asosida bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining harakat faolligini takomillashtirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyati.....	244
Hafizov Shahriyor Shavkatovich	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning transversal: tanqidiy va innovatsion fikrlash kompetensiyalari	248
Jaloliddinova Maftunaxon Mahmudjon qizi	
Axborotning gnoseologik mohiyati.....	256
Kamolova Munajatxon Jaloldinovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish yo'llari	259
Mamatova Aziza Bo'riboevna	
Akademik litseylarda kimyo fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari....	262
Maxamadiyev Sharofiddin Jumaboyevich	
Pedagogik oliy ta'limda talabalarning kasbiy ijtimoiylashuvini korporativ madaniyat asosida rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	267
Maxkamova Dilafuz Aliyevna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda lingvomadaniy yondashuv	271
Normamatova Kamola Gulmamat qizi	
O'zbek tili izohli lug'atida iboralarning grammatik tavsifi (bosh komponentli iboralar misolida).....	274
S. Sh. Azamatova	
Oila instituti va gender tenglikni ta'minlashning ijtimoiy-huquqiy muammolari	277
Salayeva Aziza Muhammadmurot qizi	
Gender yondashuv asosida talaba-qizlarda tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning namunaviy mezonlari.....	282
Xolova Mohigul Shavkatovna	
Pedagogika yo'nalishi talabalari huquqiy savodxonligini rivojlantirish metodlarini takomillashtirish.....	287
Xudoyberganov Atham	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida leksik komponentlikni TRIZ texnologiyasi yordamida rivojlantirish	291
Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna, Fayzullayeva Nazokat Uchqun qizi	
Цифровизация и трансформация образования как социально-педагогическое явление	295
Кадирова Наргиза Азаматовна	
Методика формирования креативного мышления у студентов-филологов на основе проблемно-ориентированных заданий (на материале английского языка)	298
Мамырбаева Дина	
Bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari	304
Mamadjonova Sakina Mo'minjonovna, Maxmudova Oygul Toxirjonovna	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda morfologik kompetentlikni shakllantirish	309
Ganiyeva Shodiya Azizovna	
Модель "4+1+1" как ключевой механизм в системе практической подготовки учителей музыки.....	313
Мухитдинова Малохатхон Саиджабборовна	
Tarbiya fanini o'qish samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish	317
Nazarova Nasiba Abdullayevna	
Tarbiyachining kasbiy psixologik xususiyatlari.....	320
Shamshetova Anjim Karamaddinovna	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda tarbiya nazariyasi va metodologiyasi	323
Bo'ronova Iroda Bo'ronovna	
Yosh dzyudochi qizlarning mashg'ulotlar jarayonida jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirish texnologiyalari	327
Matmurotova Iroda Baxtiyor qizi	
"Odob us-solihin" asarida yoritilgan axloqiy-didaktik g'oyalar va uning pedagogik mazmuni.....	332
A. N. Nusratov	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini kasbiy kompetentligini takomillashtirishning metodik asoslari	336
Xolmatov Pardaboy Qoraboevich, Abdurasulova Dilnoza	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari faoliyatida loyihalashtirishning o'rni	342
<i>Abdusattorova Go'zalxon Abdulxabib qizi</i>	
Tibbiyot va frazeologiya inson omilida	346
<i>Achilov Muzaffar Norquliyevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida fazoviy tasavvurlarni rivojlantirishda matematikaning ahamiyati	349
<i>Mamasaidova Muhabbat Abdulalom qizi, Akbaraliyeva Marjona Xurshid qizi</i>	
Ekoestetik kompetensiyani shakllantirishning xorijiy va milliy tajribalar tahlili	354
<i>Alijonova Maftuna Maxamadjon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik jarayonda talabalarda qadriyatli munosabatlarni shakllantirish mexanizmlari	359
<i>Alikulova Muxayyo Sherovna</i>	
Ingliz ritsarlik romanlarining lingvopoetik tahlili	362
<i>Durdona Boychayeva, Aliyeva Elmira</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda estetik tarbiya berishning pedagogik asoslari	365
<i>Altibayeva Gulbaxor Majitovna</i>	
Kasbiy kompetensiya tushunchasining mazmuni mohiyati va tarkibiy tuzilmasi	369
<i>Axmadjonova Jasmira Jamshid qizi</i>	
Developing Writing Competence Among CEFR B1 and Ielts Learners Experiencing Difficulties in English Language Acquisition	374
<i>Ayturayev Majid Mavlankhanovich</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida ijtimoiy intellektni rivojlantirishning milliy qadriyatlarga asoslangan modeli	378
<i>Azamov Umarxon Yaxyoxonovich</i>	
Complications in Teaching Argumentative Speech to Students in Grades 8–9	383
<i>Buribayeva Aziza Ismatillaevna</i>	
Interfaol o'yinlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-emotsional ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari	386
<i>Buriyeva Aziza Nematovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning ijodiy faolligini shakllantirish	390
<i>Davronova Sevinch</i>	
O'quvchilarda milliy va umummadaniy kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda maqollardan foydalanish bo'yicha manbaalar tahlili	394
<i>Boltayeva Barno, Eliboyeva Surayyo Abdulkarim qizi</i>	
Social Roots and Psychological Consequences of Domestic Violence	399
<i>Dumarova Gulmira Kozimbekovna, Mamadaliyeva Gulmira, Sultonova Zulhayo</i>	
The Transversal-Methodical Competence of a Preschool Educator is the Foundation of Effective And Quality Education	402
<i>Ergasheva Barno Ziyavitdin kizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berishning innovatsion yo'llari	406
<i>Erkinova Mehriniso Ro'ziboyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini oshirish strategiyalari	411
<i>Eshonkulova Hilola Rajab qizi</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi muloqotning bilish faoliyatiga ta'siri	415
<i>Habibova Shyira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida o'qish buzilishlarini aniqlash va bartaraf etish	419
<i>Ikromova Sarvinoz Siroj qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda riskologik kompetentlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	424
<i>Jabborova Dilafuz Furqatovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda chet tili o'rganish jarayonida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning psixologik asoslari	428
<i>Jurayeva Sug'diyona Shamsiddin qizi</i>	
Transforming Education: The Impact of Emerging Technologies on Modern Pedagogical Practices	431
<i>Kadirova Ferangiz Himmatillo qizi</i>	
Salomatlik etikasi konsepsiyasi va pedagogik madaniyat – talabalar ma'naviyati va dunyoqarashini shakllantirishdagi roli	435
<i>Kamalova Yoqutxon Bahodirovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Tarbiyachilarning kasbiy mahoratini takomillashtirish va pedagogik faoliyat samaradorligini oshirish omillari 439 Kenjayeva Dildora Terkashevna Maktab ta'lim tizimida innovatsiyalarning o'rni va ahamiyati 443 Kistabayeva Gulchexra Djurakulovna Kichik maktab yoshi davrida o'quv faoliyati va o'quv motivlarining shakllanishi 448 Latifa Zarifovna Korayeva Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimining raqamlashtirilishi: xalqaro tajriba va istiqbollar 451 Mahmudova Zulfiya Homidovna, Hoshimova Dilnoza Boymirzoevna Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini dizayn tafakkurga o'rgatishda STEAM yondashuvining didaktik imkoniyatlari 454 Mamadaminova Munisa Maxmudjon qizi, Boboxonova Shodiyona Rustam qizi Tabiatni asrash – kelajakni asrash: Buxoro misolida 459 Mardonova Saodat Muzaffarovna Bo'lajak pedagoglarda o'z-o'zini baholash kompetentligini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish 463 Meyliyeva Nafosat Gulomovna Sun'iy intellektning ta'limda kognitiv va metakognitiv jarayonlarga ta'siri 466 Murodov Ulug'bek O'tkir o'g'li Maktabgacha ta'limda inklyuziv ta'limning tashkil etilishi 470 Mustofoyeva Muhabbat Husniddin qizi The Effectiveness of Art Therapy in Working With Children Experiencing Emotional Stress 473 Nargiza Khayrullayevna Ortikova, Laziz Azizovich Normuratov Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyalanuvchilarining musiqiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari 477 Ortiqov Akmaljon Abdusalom o'g'li CLIL metodining O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida qo'llanilishi 481 Qarshiyeva Sarvinoz Ural qizi The Use of Mobile Apps to Build Vocabulary Proficiency 486 Kosimov Sunnat Ravshan ugli Yoshlar tafakkurini rivojlantirish va ma'naviyatini oshirishda tasviriy san'atning o'rni 490 Quvonchbek Abduxamidov Axborot texnologiyalari ta'sirida san'at tushunchasining o'zgarishi 494 Rajabova Laylo O'tkir qizi Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari 498 Ramozonova Bahoroy Sadriddinovna Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlarning pedagogik asoslari 501 Yusufzoda Shabnami Yunus, Rashidova Saida Ravshonbek qizi Axborot texnologiyalarini fizika darslarida qo'llash 506 Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li Axborot xavfsizligini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish afzalliklari 510 Raxmetova Lazzat Eshitishda nuqsonli bo'lgan bolalarning psixologik xususiyatlarining o'ziga xosligi 513 S. A. Mamatisayeva Androgogik yondashuvning integrativ metodikasi 517 Sattorova Shaxlo Axadovna Gendered Language in Uzbek and English Media Discourse 520 Sultonova Charos Iskandar kizi Maktabga tayyorlov yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy ekologik dunyoqarashni shakllantirishga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar 527 Suyunova Matluba Abdusaidovna Empatiya shifokor–pasiyent munosabatida: tibbiyot talabalarining psixologik tayyorgarligi 531 Tajiboyeva Odinoxon Rustamjon qizi, Qurbonova Fotima Farhodjon qizi Modern Approaches to Teaching Grammar 534 Tuychiyev Azamat Farkhod ugli The Importance of Psychological Preparation of Preschool Children for School Education 538 Turamov Muhammadzohid Rustamjon o'g'li
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Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachi-pedagoglarining kasbiy-axloqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish	541
<i>Xabibullayeva Sayyoraxon Maxamadali qizi</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan va sog'lom bolalar faoliyatida universal ta'limning imkoniyati	544
<i>Xolmatova Sarvinoz Raxmatilla qizi</i>	
Kurashchilarning umumiy va maxsus sport tayyorgarliklari.....	548
<i>Xudoyberganov Javlonbek Soatboy o'g'li</i>	
Tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarida ekologik kompetentlik tushunchalarini rivojlantirish bosqichlari.....	551
<i>Yarova Gulhayo Fazliddin qizi</i>	
Arxitektura va dizayn yo'nalishi bitiruvchilarini kasbga yo'naltirish vositasida axborot almashish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	555
<i>Kuchimov M. K.</i>	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ma'naviy kompetentligini jadidlarning pedagogik qarashlari asosida shakllantirish metodikasi (Temurbeklar maktablari misolida)	559
<i>Quldashev Murodjon G'aniyevich</i>	
Лингвистическое исследование влияния социальных сетей на синтаксические изменения в языке современного поколения.....	562
<i>Шавилова Наталья Сергеевна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining nutq madaniyati.....	566
<i>Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna, Gulimbayeva Barno</i>	
Особенности гражданского воспитания обучающихся в системе “школа–махаля” в Узбекистане ...	570
<i>Хайдаров Шавкат Шамсиддин угли</i>	
Mantiqiy masalalarni bajarishning metodik usullari	575
<i>Tosheva Yulduz</i>	
Bo'lajak ofitserlarni harbiy-vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalashda pedagogik-psixologik omillar (jamoat xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'linmalari misolida)	579
<i>Yarmatov Akbar Normurotovich</i>	
Yosh harbiy xizmatchi ofitserlarda muloqot madaniyatini samarali shakllantirish muammosining xorijiy tadqiqotlardagi talqini	582
<i>Matyakubov Elyor Rajapovich</i>	
Umumiy pedagogika fanini o'qitishda formativ baholash metodikasini joriy etish texnologiyasi	586
<i>Sobitjon Xalimov Hoshimjonovich</i>	
Формирование компонентов эмоционального интеллекта у детей дошкольного возраста с дефектами речи на основе сказкотерапии	590
<i>Эркинова Фазилат Миразиз қизи</i>	
O'zbekistonda asalarichilikning rivojlanishi.....	593
<i>Abdullayeva Maxsudaxon To'lanovna</i>	
14–16 yoshli dzyudochilarda hujum kombinatsiyalari va ularni musobaqaviy sharoitda qo'llash usullarini takomillashtirish.....	596
<i>Abduraxmanova Iroda Xayrullayevna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda aksiologik tarbiya mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish ijtimoiy ehtiyoj va pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	602
<i>B. S. Siddikov</i>	
Sport mashg'ulotlar davomida mushak va suyak tizimi rivojlanishi	606
<i>Bo'ronova Habiba Erkin qizi</i>	
Stol tennis o'yini texnikasi.....	609
<i>Ibragimov Abduqahhor Abdulaziz o'g'li</i>	
Biologiya fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy platformalarning afzalliklari: Wordwall, Educaplay, Blooket, Genially, Kahoot platformalari	613
<i>Kalandarova Dilnoza Samandarovna, Qodirova Madina Nosirovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida tahsil olayotgan paraarmrestlingchi talabalarni musobaqa oldidan texnik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish	617
<i>Karimov Faxriddin Xurramovich</i>	
Developing Critical Reading Skills Through Content-Based Instruction.....	621
<i>Mekhmonkulov Burkhon Ma'ruf ugli</i>	
Tog'li va shahar hududida ta'lim oluvchi tinglovchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasini taqqoslash	626
<i>Mirjamolov Sirojiddin Xayriddinovich</i>	

Korxonada va tashkilotlarda ishchi-xodimlarning jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish asosida ish faolligini oshirish texnologiyasi	630
Muxametov Axmad Muxametovich	
Xalq ta'limi bo'limi rahbarlarining xalqaro baholash tizimini O'zbekiston ta'limiga moslashtirishdagi o'rni	634
Namazova Manzura Urakovna, Nodirov Dilmurod	
Digital Reading vs. Print Reading: Effects on EFL Learners' Reading Speed and Understanding	639
Rustambekova Ozoda Dilshod kizi	
Yoshlarning jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlariga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshirishning samarali usullari	644
To'rayev Farrux Hakim o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalaridagi talaba-qizlarni dzyudo sport turi texnik harakatlariga o'rgatish texnologiyasi	647
Toshboyeva Munisa Bozor qizi	
Sport mashg'ulotlarda jarohatlarning oldini olish va xavfsizlik choralarini	650
Xudoyberdiyeva Elmira Botir qizi	
Задачи изучения и преподавания русского языка и литературы в общеобразовательных школах с узбекским языком обучения	654
Ahmedov Humon	
Multimedia va infografika asosida interaktiv didaktik materiallar yaratish	658
Shirinov Feruzjon Shuxratovich, Rahmonov Ziyodillo Xusanovich	
Ingliz tili darslarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining talaffuz ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi (immitativ-taqiidiy usul misolida)	661
Jo'rayeva Dilafuz Nuriddinova	
O'simliklarning issiqqa va qurqoqchilikka chidamliligi	664
M. Nazarov, G. Maxsudova, T. Usmonova	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning jismoniy tayyorgarligi hamda psixik jarayonlar ko'rsatkichlarining tahlili	667
Masharipova Miyassar Ichanovna	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni "Tabiat bilan tanishtirish" fani asosida tarbiyaviy faoliyatini raqamlashtirish	675
Saydullayeva Barchinoy Abduxalil qizi	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida faoliyat yuritishga tayyorlash muammolari	678
Shaxnoza To'xtiyarova	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida o'quv resurslarini yaratishning raqamli-didaktik mazmunini rivojlantirish metodikasi	681
Shirinov Feruzjon Shuxratovich	
Umumta'lim maktablarining 9-sinf fizika darslarida tovush hodisasini anglashni tajriba orqali rivojlantirish	684
Sobirov Avazbek Anvarovich	
Emotsional intellekt tushunchasining nazariy asoslari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	689
Tajiboyeva Odinoxon Rustamjon qizi	
Portret janrini o'qitishda individual ta'lim va fanlararo integratsiyaning nazariy-metodologik asoslari	693
Xudaynazarova Ug'illov Sharifovna	
Aqli zaif bolalarda sensomotor rivojlanishning psixologik-pedagogik xususiyatlari	696
Xudoyberdiyeva Ra'no Arabboyevna	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarida estetik madaniyatni tarbiyalash metodikasi (tarbiya fani misolida)	700
Yoqubjonova Shodiya G'ayratovna	
Chizmachilik fanining turmush tarzimidagi ahamiyati va o'rni	704
Achilov Nurbek Norboy o'g'li	
O'quvchilarni musiqa san'atiga qiziqtirishda musiqa psixologiyasining roli	707
E'zozxon Qobilova	
Bolalar adabiyotini o'qitishda milliy qadriyatlarni singdirish va kreativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning innovatsion yo'llari	710
G'aniyeva Shodiya Azizovna, Abdullayeva Madinaxon Madaminjon qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf darsliklarida berilgan mashqlarni til kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish maqsadida tahlil qilish	713
G'anijonova Sarvinov, Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna	
O'quvchilarda global o'qish savodxonligini shakllantirishda milliy matnlar va qadriyatlar asosidagi pirls tipidagi topshiriqlar yaratish tajribasi	717
Ikromova Gulhida Axmadillo qizi, G'ofurova Dilshodaxon Toxirjon qizi	

Bo'lajak pedagoglarni intellektual rivojlantirishda pedagogik artistizmdan foydalanish texnologiyalari pedagogik muammo sifatida	720
<i>Karribayeva Lobarxon Fayzulla qizi</i>	
Ilmiy matnni o'qib tushunish va baholashda nostandart testlardan foydalanish bosqichlari.....	724
<i>Komilova Lola Nasilloevna</i>	
Dizartriya davosida tovushlar talaffuzidagi kamchiliklarni o'yin orqali rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	728
<i>Mamatova Muzayyana Batirovna</i>	
Turkiy bitiklarda nomlar tizimi va ularning semantik xususiyatlari	732
<i>Munisa Shavkatova</i>	
Kommunikativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarni mediatorlik faoliyatiga tayyorlash texnologiyasini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	736
<i>Muqimova Dilbarxon Xusanboyevna</i>	
Sportda liderlik va jamoaviy ruhni shakllantirish metodlari	740
<i>Nazarov Nursultan Safarbayevich</i>	
Dars mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishda loyihalashtirishning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	744
<i>Normurodov Sharofiddin Muxiddinovich</i>	
Ta'limda innovatsion kompetentlikning ahamiyati.....	748
<i>Qobilova Aziza Tursunovna</i>	
Innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari orqali bolalarda tanqidiy va ijodiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish	752
<i>Salimova Aziza Sharipovna</i>	
Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda masofaviy ta'limning imkoniyatlari va muammolari	755
<i>Sidiqova Ma'mura Adhamjonovna</i>	
Til kompetentligini rivojlantirishda vizual materiallardan foydalanishning o'rni (boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini oshirish texnologiyasi misolida)	758
<i>Zokirova Sohiba Muhtoralievna, Sobirova Diloromxon Ma'rufjon qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi ko'xlear implantli bolalarni eshituv - nutqiy reabilitatsiyasi	761
<i>Xamraeva Dildora Baxadirovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda duduqlanishni kelib chiqish sababalari va korreksion ishlar	766
<i>Xolboeva Ruxsora Egamberdiyevna</i>	
Эффективность арт-терапии в обогащении словарного запаса у детей с ЗПП	770
<i>Наган Олеся Талгатовна</i>	
Autizmli bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda o'yinning ahamiyati.....	775
<i>Nishonova Sevara</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda disgrafiyasi bo'lgan o'quvchilarda yozish kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari (XIX–XXI asrda).....	778
<i>Qaxxorova Saidaxon, Mamarajabova Zulfiya</i>	
Autizmli bolalarda kommunikativ muloqotni shakllantirish texnologiyalari.....	781
<i>Raxmonova Manzura Maxmudovna</i>	
Talabalarda ma'naviy ongning rivojlanishidagi milliy dunyoqarash va tafakkur uslubining shakllanish omillari	785
<i>Usarova Nigora Berdiyevna</i>	
PIRLSda qo'llaniladigan yuqori darajadagi tushunish ko'nikmalari (interpretatsiya, sintez) va ularni muloqotga o'rgatishda qo'llash	788
<i>Choriyeva Valida Abdug'ani qizi, Shodiyev Faxriddin Teshayevich</i>	
Prokrastinatsiya fenomenining retrospektiv talqini	795
<i>M. L. Aripova</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda millatlararo totuvlikni shakllantirishda badiiy adabiyotning o'rni.....	799
<i>Xudoyberdiyeva Madina Abdulbaki qizi</i>	
Malakali futbolchilarni tayyorlashning innovatsion pedagogik va texnologik uslublari.....	802
<i>Maxmudov Mamat Raxmatovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda madaniy qadriyatlarga hurmat hissini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	807
<i>Adolat Xolmatova Muxammadjonovna</i>	
Oliy ta'limda inklyuziv qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda maxsus pedagogikaning o'rni	811
<i>Alijonova Dilorom Azamjonovna</i>	
Sportning kurash turi tarixi, nazariy asoslari va zamonaviy rivojlanish yo'nalishlari.....	815
<i>Do'stov Dilmurod Karimovich</i>	

MUNDARIJA SOÐERJANIE CONTENTS	O'quvchi qizlarni oliy ta'lim muassasalariga yo'naltirishda ota-onalar bilan ishlashning kollaborativ usullari 818 Egamberdiyev Umidbek Xo'jayevich
The Effectiveness of Art Therapy in Working With Children Experiencing Emotional Stress 821 Ortikova Nargiza Xayrullayevna, Normuratov Laziz Azizovich	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tovush talaffuzi buzilishining turlarini va darajasini aniqlash usullari 826 Otaboyeva Nodira Qodir qizi	
Ta'limda innovatsion kompetentlikning ahamiyati 830 Qobilova Aziza Tursunovna	
Intellektual madaniyatni rivojlantirishda integrativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash texnologiyalari 833 Qurbonov Jasurbek Akmaljonovich	
Biologiya, kimyo va geografiya fanlarni o'qitishda iqtidorli o'quvchilarda ekologik madaniyatni shakllantirish 837 Sultanova N. B., Toshpo'latova N. I., Azimov B. I.	
Методика развития навыков самостоятельного обучения учащихся с помощью онлайн-образовательных платформ 840 Суяров Хуршид Бахриддинович	
Oliy ta'limda sun'iy intellektni boshqarishda rivojlangan chet davlatlar tajribasidan foydalanish usullari 844 Tajetdinova Gulnara Abatbay qizi	
Variativ yondashuv asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida dialogik nutqni rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari 852 Turapova Ra'no Barat qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida tarbiyalanuvchilarga og'zaki hisoblashni o'rgatish 857 Jurayeva Muhayyo Nematillayevna	
Trening jarayonidagi muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari 861 Nodirova M. B., Usmanova S. A., Vaxidova U. A.	
Pedagogika oliy o'quv yurtlarida tahsil olayotgan talabalarining sport faoliyati turlari orqali innovatsion texnologiyalarini takomillashtirish 865 Turdiyev Umidjon Kamoliddinovich	
Badiiy adabiyot vositasida nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda dialogik nutq shakllarini shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari 868 Umarova Muhayyo Abdusattor qizi, Mamarajabova Zulfiya Narboyevna	
The Role of Family Support in Fostering Individual Resilience Against Social Offenses (An Integration of Continuing Education, National Values, and Personal Narratives) 873 Khoshimov Lutfullo Khabibullo ugli	
Milliy kiyimlarni zamonaviy material va konstruksiya bilan uyg'unlashtirish 877 Yuldasheva Gulsanam Arken qizi	
Преподавание русского языка в школах Узбекистана глазами будущих педагогов 881 Бахриева Шахноза Давроновна	
Методологические основы дисциплины "Госпитальной педагогики" 886 Равшанова Иноят Эркиновна	
Тропеический блок как ключевой инструмент создания образа восприятия в романе С. Моэма "The Razor's Edge" 889 Тагаева Тамара Баходировна	
Zamonaviy oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim va tarbiya integratsiyasi 892 D. S. Zokirova	
O'quvchi qizlarni oliy ta'lim muassasalariga yo'naltirishda ota-onalar bilan ishlashning kollaborativ usullari 895 Egamberdiyev Umidbek Xo'jayevich	
Umumta'lim maktablarida kimyo fani o'qitishning samarali usullari 898 Yunusov Mirzoxid Mirzakarimovich, Odilova Feruzabonu Oybek qizi, Soibjonova Gulasalxon Farhodjon qizi	
Ertak qahramonlari obrazlari orqali boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini axloqiy va kreativ fikrlash sifatlarini shakllantirish 901 Ortiqova Zulfiya Nurmuhammedovna, Dilnavoz Tojiyeva Abduvohid qizi	
Raqamli o'quv muhitida multimedia kontentini loyihalashning didaktik tamoyillari 905 Rustemov Muxamed Biysenbayevich	
The Essence and Content of The Concept of Ecological Culture 908 Sa'dullayeva Zuhra Murodullayevna	

Talabalarda raqamli refleksiyaning shakllantirishi pedagogik muammo sifatida	912
Salixova Muhayyo Shakirovna	
Kasbiy leksik kompetensiya metodikasi shakllanishining tarixiy rivojlanish asoslari	915
Tog'ayeva Maxfuza Abdunazarovna, Tilovova Gavhar Abdaxatovna	
Autizm spektori buzilishi bo'lgan bolalar tavsifi.....	920
U. M. Utbasarova	
Ta'lim jarayonida qo'llaniluvchi sun'iy intellekt vositalari haqida tushuncha	925
Xakimova Yoqutxon Toxirjon qizi, Pulatova Ziyodaxon Baxodirjon qizi	
Проблемы перевода медицинских терминов: сложности и ошибки, возникающие при переводе медицинской литературы с других языков на русский.....	928
Алибекова Лайло Рахмановна	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti direktorining mediakompetentligini integrativ yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish: model, metodologiya va empirik natijalar	931
Asqarxo'jayeva Movluda Saidmuhammadzokir qizi	
Identifying the Cause of Addiction to Alcohol and Drugs	935
Nauruzbaeva Ayjan Sarsenbaevna, Reymov Muxamedali Kengesbayevich, Kalmuratova Sara Umirzakovna	
Methods of Utilising the Legacy of Eastern Thinkers in Education.....	938
Raimova Nasiba Abdreimovna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda pedagogik muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirishda mediasavodxonlikning ahamiyati.....	942
Raximova Zulfiyaxon Xashimjonovna	
Pedagog va maxsus psixologlarni hamkorlikda tayyorlash texnologiyasining tarkibiy komponentlari va ularning xususiyatlari	949
Turg'unov Mirjalol Mirzahamdani o'g'li	
Og'ir vazn yo'qotish (weight cutting)ning organizm fiziologiyasiga salbiy ta'siri	952
Ibragimov Azizbek Ilhom o'g'li	
Языковая политика и её влияние на статус русского языка в образовательной среде Узбекистана ..	956
Бобаназарова Шоира Содиковна, Нурмаматов Бобур Ботирович	
Sun'iy intellekt didaktik ta'limot vositasi sifatida ahamiyati	961
To'raboyeva Mahliyo Qo'zimbek qizi	
Embracing Diversity in the Classroom: Inclusive Education Strategies for Empowering All Learners	964
Bahronova Maftuna Farhadovna	
Ta'lim jarayoniga xalqaro pedagogik tajribani samarali joriy etish: usullar va yondashuvlar	968
Xakimov Sodiqjon Rasuljon o'g'li	

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ART THERAPY IN WORKING WITH CHILDREN EXPERIENCING EMOTIONAL STRESS

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Abstract: The article examines the issue of studying stress in preschool-aged children. Modern children are often exposed to emotional stress caused by unfavorable conditions in the family, school, social environment, or by individual psychological characteristics. Emotional stress may manifest itself in the form of anxiety, aggression, isolation, sleep disorders, and increased attention. Art therapy is one of the most effective methods of psychological support for children in such situations. This method is based on using art as a means of self-expression and restoring emotional balance.

The article discusses how art therapy can help children cope with emotional stress. The theoretical foundations of this approach and its impact on the child's emotional state and mental health are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the mechanisms of art therapy, such as reducing anxiety, developing self-expression, and improving emotional regulation. Practical examples and corrective methods used when working with stressed children are presented. The author concludes that art therapy has high effectiveness in the system of psychological assistance for children with emotional difficulties. Based on the conducted survey, the attitudes of schoolchildren, teachers, and parents toward the causes and severity of stress were identified. The possibilities of art therapy as a means of alleviating stress in the younger generation are also analyzed.

Key words: art therapy, children, psychocorrection, emotional stress, anxiety.

Аннотатсия: Maqola maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda stress holatini o'rganish masalasiga bag'ishlangan. Zamonaviy bolalar ko'pincha oiladagi, maktabdagi, ijtimoiy muhitdagi yoki individual psixologik xususiyatlardan kelib chiqadigan noqulay omillar ta'sirida hissiy stressni boshdan kechiradilar. Hissiy stress tashvish, tajovuzkorlik, izolyatsiya, uyqu buzilishi yoki e'tiborning kuchayishi kabi holatlar orqali namoyon bo'ladi. Art-terapiya bunday vaziyatlarda bolalarni psixologik qo'llab-quvvatlashning samarali vositalaridan biridir. Ushbu yondashuv san'at orqali o'zini ifoda etish va hissiy muvozanatni tiklash imkonini beradi.

Maqolada art-terapiya yordamida bolalarning hissiy stressni yengish jarayoni tahlil qilinadi. Yondashuvning nazariy asoslari hamda uning bolaning hissiy holati va ruhiy salomatligiga ta'siri yoritilgan. Shuningdek, art-terapiyaning xavotirni kamaytirish, o'zini namoyon qilish va hissiy tartibga solishdagi mexanizmlari ilmiy jihatdan izohlangan. Stress holatidagi bolalar bilan olib boriladigan tuzatish ishlari bo'yicha amaliy misollar keltirilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari art-terapiya usulining hissiy qiyinchiliklarga duch kelgan bolalarni qo'llab-quvvatlashda yuqori samaradorligini ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, so'rov asosida o'quvchilar, o'qituvchilar va ota-onalarning stress sabablariga bo'lgan munosabatlari o'rganilgan. Art-terapiya yosh avlodagi stressni kamaytirishning samarali usuli sifatida baholangan.

Kalit so'zlar: art-terapiya, bolalar, psixokorreksiya, hissiy stress, xavotirlanish.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена изучению стрессовых состояний у детей дошкольного возраста. Современные дети часто подвергаются эмоциональному напряжению, вызванному неблагоприятными условиями в семье, школе, социальной среде или индивидуальными психологическими особенностями. Эмоциональный стресс может проявляться в виде тревожности, агрессии, замкнутости, нарушений сна и внимания. Арт-терапия является одним из наиболее эффективных методов психологической поддержки детей в подобных ситуациях. Этот метод основан на использовании искусства как средства самовыражения и восстановления эмоционального равновесия.

В статье анализируется, как арт-терапия помогает детям справляться с эмоциональным стрессом. Рассмотрены теоретические основы данного подхода и его влияние на эмоциональное состояние и психическое здоровье ребёнка. Особое внимание уделено механизмам действия арт-терапии, таким как снижение тревожности, развитие самовыражения и эмоциональной регуляции. Представлены практические примеры и методы коррекционной работы с детьми, испытывающими стресс. На основании проведённого опроса выявлены отношения школьников, учителей и родителей к причинам и степени выраженности стресса. Автор приходит к выводу о высокой эффективности арт-терапии в системе психологической помощи детям, испытывающим эмоциональные трудности, и подчёркивает её значительный потенциал как метода снижения стресса у подрастающего поколения.

Ключевые слова: арт-терапия, дети, психокоррекция, эмоциональный стресс, тревожность.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, art therapy has become an increasingly popular method of treatment and rehabilitation in various areas of medicine, including dentistry. Art therapy is a specialized form of therapy that utilizes artistic materials and techniques to promote mental and physical well-being in patients. In the field of dentistry, this type of therapy can be employed to reduce stress and anxiety related to dental treatments, as well as assist in the recovery process after various procedures.

One method of incorporating art therapy into dental care is through the creation of drawings or other forms of artwork prior to or during dental visits. This allows patients to focus on a creative outlet and divert their attention from concerns prior to treatment. Research has shown that art therapy significantly enhances the psychological well-being of patients before their dental appointments and assists them in managing pain and discomfort following procedures. Furthermore, art therapy fosters improved communication between patients and dentists, enhancing the overall effectiveness of treatment.

Art therapy serves as a valuable tool in addressing these challenges, promoting mental well-being and enhancing the quality of life for individuals.

The ongoing health crisis has also contributed to a rise in stress levels across all age groups. However, there is a specific group that is particularly susceptible to stress and its adverse effects – children, adolescents, and young adults. For this group, stress is particularly perilous, as they lack the knowledge and experience to manage stress and have not yet developed sufficient psychological defenses. It is well known that the most dangerous form of stress is not so much acute as it is prolonged, chronic stress. This is particularly relevant for students, as it poses a risk of chronic school stress. Therefore, it is crucial to prevent it in a timely manner and effectively address its consequences.

School stress can lead to maladaptive states in children, which manifest as passivity, self-doubt, and feelings of inadequacy. This can result in depression, alienation, negative attitudes towards others and society, and compensatory aggression. In extreme cases, this can underlie socially dangerous behaviors such as bullying, violence, and exposure to extreme ideologies. Compensatory aggression may also be directed towards other ethnic and religious groups, leading to extremism and terrorism. However, these are rare instances. In most cases, school stress and maladaptation hinder the full realization of a child's creative potential and personal

growth. This can lead to future school difficulties, which can block motivation and activity, as well as hinder the development of a student's abilities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, art therapy has become an increasingly recognized psychological and rehabilitative method in medicine and education, especially in working with children experiencing emotional tension. Nargiza Ortikova, in her research, has scientifically substantiated the significance of art therapy in reducing psycho-emotional stress in children. In her work *Influence of Psycho-Emotional Stress on Children on the State of Health of the Oral Cavity*, she proved that art therapy not only helps to reduce emotional stress but also positively influences children's overall well-being. Moreover, in *The Relationship of Dental Anxiety with Demographic Indicators*, Ortikova emphasizes that art therapy effectively alleviates fear and anxiety related to medical and dental visits, fostering a sense of emotional security in children.

According to Axatov Alijon Jamshidovich and Ortikova Nargiza Khayrullayevna, art therapy plays a significant role in activating emotional defense mechanisms and developing positive communication skills in children. Their study *Emotional and Behavioral Reactions Are a Manifestation of Protection in Children When Visiting a Dentist* highlights the diagnostic and preventive potential of art therapy in clinical settings. Similarly, in *Dental Anxiety as a Special Place in Scientific Knowledge*, Ortikova notes that art therapy represents a scientifically grounded method for psychological correction and should be integrated more widely into medical and educational practices.

The analysis of these studies demonstrates that art therapy effectively reduces stress, anxiety, and emotional tension while enhancing children's psychological stability and communication abilities. Ortikova's publication *Tendentsiya effektivnosti profilakticheskikh meropriyatiy putem korreksii psixologicheskogo stressa u detey na stomatologicheskom prieme* presents scientific evidence that this method contributes to the healthy psychological development of children. Therefore, the use of art therapy in educational and medical practice is an important approach to promoting emotional well-being, creativity, and resilience among children.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on a qualitative and analytical approach. Data were obtained through structured observations, psychological assessments, and interviews with children, parents, and teachers. The collected information was analyzed using comparative and descriptive methods to determine the effectiveness of art therapy in reducing emotional stress and improving children's psychological well-being.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Stress is an emotional and physiological response to demands placed on the individual, which can be expressed in terms of the mobilization of internal resources to cope with these demands. School-related stress, in particular, arises from the demands imposed on students by the educational process. This can lead to complex situations in which students do not have adequate resources to cope, potentially threatening their mental and physical well-being. When left unaddressed, such stress can result in resource depletion and exhaustion.

Psychoemotional stress, a specific type of stress, is characterized by an increase in physiological and psychological activity, with one of its key features being extreme instability. Under adverse conditions, stress can lead to a state of psychological and emotional strain, characterized by reduced efficiency and effectiveness of systems and organs and, most importantly, rapid depletion of energy resources in the body.

Experience shows that art therapy can significantly improve the psychological state of patients before a dental visit and help them cope with pain and discomfort afterwards. In addition, art therapy improves communication between doctors and patients, which increases treatment effectiveness. One of the most effective ways to deal with emotional stress in children is regular art classes. Visual arts and drama classes, both passive (contemplation, experiencing art phenomena) and active (creating artistic works), not only have an aesthetic impact but also help individuals build an adequate psychological protection system.

Artistic activities give everyone a chance to feel like creators, to use art to deal with negative experiences, and to model communication both with their own work and with others in group projects. Visual activities also create a positive environment for developing an emotional connection with art, which, in turn, helps form a positive attitude towards the world. The goal of art therapy, based on psychoanalysis, is to help people understand their problems through their own creations. This can be enough to overcome those problems.

The psychoanalytic approach does not involve the development of practical skills in artistic expression. This means that a person can consciously and actively understand themselves and others, make changes to themselves, and be free from being a slave to external circumstances. They can also change the environment around them instead of simply adapting to it.

Art therapy provides an opportunity to create an inner world that includes experiences, safe challenges, and problems that can be solved. The process begins with drawing, creating engravings, installing artworks, performing plays, taking photographs, or sculpting in clay. These creations are then brought into the person's everyday life.

Working with various means of artistic expression, such as color, a person can learn about their nature and methods of application. Through this process, they can find solutions to problems and gain the ability to design their own lives independently. In our country, art therapy has only recently begun to work with at-risk adolescents, people with disabilities, and victims of terrorist attacks. It started about 10–15 years ago, and programs are still being developed, and projects are being proposed.

To conduct art therapy, specialists need a deeper understanding and skills in different types of artistic activities. We have created an art therapy program to help people deal with stress and its negative emotional effects. Art therapy, which involves using art or creativity, has long been considered one of the most effective ways to improve psychoemotional well-being. After all, expressing emotions, feelings, and moods is a natural part of being human, and drawing, like other creative activities, can help relieve psychoemotional stress.

Art therapy is a form of psychotherapy that utilizes the creation and analysis of artistic works. Art therapy techniques, such as drawing therapy, aim to promote self-awareness, emotional processing, and positive attitude formation through visual means. Drawing therapy is a common practice in art therapy that involves using drawing as a means of expression and communication. Through drawing, individuals can express their feelings, thoughts, and desires, as well as explore and reframe their relationships with various situations and challenging images. Drawing can also serve as a tool for understanding one's inner world and the external reality, as well as for modeling relationships and conveying various emotions. Drawing has been shown to be effective in reducing mental tension, managing stress, and addressing neuroses and phobias.

Drawing is a great way to unwind and release tension, going back to more primitive forms of expression and satisfying hidden desires. It helps to process and deal with negative emotions, especially for those who cannot easily express themselves verbally. One can use drawing to project inner thoughts and feelings onto the canvas, allowing exploration of one's unique perspective on the world.

Art therapy is especially helpful for children, as it helps them express their thoughts and feelings in a more creative way. It can help them deal with difficult emotions and issues and allows them to be more in touch with their inner self. It is even used with very young children, helping them develop their own unique style and personality.

Overall, drawing and art therapy are great tools for self-expression and self-discovery. They allow us to explore our inner world and find our own unique voice while also dealing with negative emotions and finding inner harmony. Moreover, creating something independently is an excellent way to boost confidence.

The process of drawing itself teaches children to focus on their feelings, be aware of their emotions, and express them in an appropriate manner, including expressing negative emotions. Art therapy enhances children's ability to express themselves and communicate their experiences with adults. There are various approaches to art therapy, such as identifying with what is drawn, drawing without intention or following one's hand, and "collective drawing," which is particularly effective at the beginning stages of training, as it aids in team building and fostering trust. It is important to note that there are no contraindications or restrictions to this technique. Art therapy provides everyone with the opportunity to express their inner world through creative expression.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Given the significance of this issue and the potential risks associated with its consequences, it is essential that training future educators include proficiency in techniques for preventing and mitigating school-related anxiety. Art therapy has been shown to be an effective method for reducing stress and anxiety among patients in dental clinics. This technique helps to enhance communication between dental professionals and patients, as well as fosters a more positive atmosphere during treatment sessions. The implementation of art therapy within the dental field can significantly enhance the quality of patient care and satisfaction. By promoting this approach, dentists can contribute to reducing patient stress and increasing the success of treatment interventions. Awareness of their emotions, coping with them often becomes a problem for many. Art therapy allows you to use creativity to realize, live and express your emotions and feelings.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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